

THE DISTRIBUTION OF MATERIAL EXCAVATED BY THE SOUTH POLE–AITKEN BASIN–FORMING IMPACT: PREDICTIONS FROM 3D NUMERICAL MODELLING. C. A. Bill¹, G. S. Collins¹, T. M. Davison¹, B. C. Johnson² and S. Wakita², ¹Department of Earth Science & Engineering, Imperial College London, Exhibition Road, SW7 2AZ (c.bill23@imperial.ac.uk). ²Department of Earth, Atmospheric and Planetary Sciences, Purdue University.

Introduction: The South Pole–Aitken (SPA) Basin is the Moon’s largest and oldest known impact crater, measuring over 2000 km in diameter [1-2]. Its formation had far-reaching consequences for the Moon’s interior structure and surface evolution. Numerical modelling studies predict that the impact excavated and redistributed deep lunar material across the surface [3-6]. Determining the distribution of this material will improve interpretations of the SPA basin and help identify potential mantle-derived materials on the Moon. Upcoming missions, including Artemis III and Chang’e-7, may provide new insights into these materials and the formation of this farside basin.

Previous 3-D modelling studies suggest that the SPA Basin was most likely formed by an oblique impact with an angle of $\sim 30^\circ$ to the target plane [6-8]. The observed elongation of the basin [1-2] is consistent with an oblique impact trajectory directed either northwards or southwards (e.g., [9, 10]). Recent work suggests the trajectory may align with a pre-existing lunar dichotomy between the lunar magma ocean region and the farside highlands [10]. The redistribution of crustal and mantle materials during the impact is sensitive to both the assumed impact conditions and the rheological and thermal structure of the lunar target [7]. Both 2D and 3D numerical modelling studies of the SPA basin formation favour a warmer, lower strength target (e.g., [3, 6-7]). Identifying mantle or deeply excavated material associated with the SPA impact would therefore provide important constraints on both the impact conditions and the early evolution of the Moon.

Here we use 3D numerical simulations to investigate how crustal, mantle, and projectile materials are redistributed during the SPA basin–forming impact.

Methods: 3D numerical simulations of SPA basin formation were conducted using iSALE-3D [11, 12], as described in Davison et al. [5]. Simulations tested impactor velocities of 10–20 km/s, radii of 75–130 km, impact angles of 20–45°, and target thermal gradients of 10–50 K/km, with upper mantle temperatures of 1400–1700 K. The Moon was modelled as three layers: a 350 km radius iron core, a dunite mantle, and a 40–50 km thick granitic crust, using ANEOS-derived equations of state [13–16] and strength models from [3]. Impactors were differentiated spheres (dunite mantle + 1/3rd by mass iron core). Simulations ran up to 5 hours post-impact, until the crustal motions were complete.

Post-impact material distributions were calculated from simulation results for comparison with lunar datasets. Radial profiles from the lunar centre were sampled in $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ bins to the surface, from which maps of integrated crustal thickness, excavated mantle, projectile material, and topography were generated. Lagrangian tracers tracked also the redistribution of crust, mantle, and projectile material throughout the simulations. Simulation fit was evaluated by calculating the misfit between GRAIL crustal thickness data [17] and simulated across- and along-range profiles, constraining the most likely impact scenarios based on crustal thickness and crater planform.

Figure 1: Snapshots from an iSALE-3D simulation at different timesteps for a 200 km diameter impactor striking a 30 K/km target with a 1700 K mantle at a 30° impact angle and 11.1 km s⁻¹ velocity. The impact direction is toward the upper left (arrow) and the outer rim of the basin (dashed outline) is shown in the final snapshot.

Results and Discussion: Our current best-fit scenarios employ a warm (30 K/km +) crust, a 200 km diameter impactor, either a 20° or 30° impact angle, and a hot (1700 K) mantle.

Crust distribution. In these best-fit scenarios, the warm crust rafts inward to cover exposed lunar mantle within 5 hours of impact (Figure 1). The thickness of this secondary crust is consistent with present-day observations [17]. Crustal material is ejected from the crater centre and distributed downrange in a butterfly pattern, reaching thicknesses of 5–10 km around the basin rim. This contributes to a broad annulus of thickened crust surrounding the basin that relaxes during the simulation as the crust continues to respond dynamically to the impact.

Figure 2: Integrated mantle thickness within the top 5 km of the surface at the end of the simulation for a scenario employing a 200 km diameter impactor, striking a 30 K/km 1700 K mantle target at 11.1 km/s and a 30 degree angle. The arrow shows the impact point and direction. The ellipses are adopted from [2] and centred at the widest point of the simulated basin.

Excavated Lunar Mantle. Mantle is exposed at the centre of the basin during the excavation stage whilst the overlying crust is removed (Figure 1c). A curtain of mantle ejecta (Figure 1c-e) emplaces mantle above the crust. A further volume of mantle is excavated and emplaced onto the lunar surface during the collapse of the central uplift. As the crust continues to oscillate post impact, some of this material becomes entrained within the upper crust and is transported away from its initial landing location (Figure 1f-j). Only a fraction of the excavated SPA mantle remains exposed at the surface at the end of the simulation (Figure 1j), but a significant volume of mantle is mixed within the uppermost 5-km of the crust (Figure 2). The volume of mantle excavated by both processes increases with impact energy but decreases for more oblique (grazing) impacts onto a spherical target. For a 20° impact angle, only a small volume is emplaced at the basin

centre during central uplift collapse, whereas for a 30° impact angle, tens of thousands of km³ are excavated to the surface through both ejection and central uplift collapse. As with the crust, mantle material is distributed in a butterfly pattern downrange of the impact point, with the thickest distribution within and around the rim of the basin (Figure 2).

Projectile Distribution. Projectile material is also distributed predominantly downrange, with iron from the projectile core concentrated around the downrange basin rim.

Ongoing and future work. The precise trajectory of the SPA impact and therefore the ultimate distribution of excavated SPA material on the Moon remain uncertain. Future simulations will investigate the effects of a pre-impact crustal and thermal dichotomy to better constrain the impact direction and the fate of excavated mantle and crustal material. These results will improve predictions of SPA material distributions and provide new insights into the role of the SPA impact in the Moon’s early evolution.

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